

Why science cannot explain consciousness

Johan Hansson*
Division of Physics
Luleå University of Technology
SE-971 87 Luleå, Sweden

This article really only needs one single sentence, the boxed one at the end. However, to supply some background I will (consciously!) add a few more sentences.

The prevailing thinking today is that consciousness somehow “emerges” [1] from mindless matter and known natural laws in some magical [2] way¹, perhaps due to some nonlinear, complex self-organization of unknown origin. I show it is *not* unknown, but scientifically *unknowable*.

Another, exactly opposite, idea [3] is that everything contains consciousness, even atoms, but consciousness becomes obviously manifest in a select few organisms, perhaps(?) only humans. But this still does not explain how/why the smallest units of consciousness arise.

Just like there in mathematics are things that are unknowable [4] so there are things that science cannot answer. But consciousness vs. science is even worse than that. In mathematics you are free to (consciously!) choose axioms, the mathematical impossibility arises *outside* consciousness. In science the impossibility arises *inside* (conscious thought itself trying to explain consciousness) and thwarts *any* attempts to explain consciousness in a scientific way. Consciousness is, and must be, taken as a given for science to even work.

The (usually hidden/forgotten) assumption of science is that scientists are conscious, *i.e.*, free to construct models, design experiments, make measurements, interpret results, convey/explain this to other (conscious!) humans, and so on. So, this is just the classic error of assuming from the outset the very thing you want to deduce - a perfect example of circular reasoning, explaining consciousness with consciousness. It is also self-referential, a little

*c.johan.hansson@ltu.se

¹If consciousness is necessary to finally make a “measurement” outcome become real in quantum mechanics consciousness cannot be (quantum) physical.

like “*This statement is false*”; if it’s true it’s false, and if it’s false it’s true. But in our case it is even worse as it disqualifies *all* of science from ever explaining consciousness. We can understand undecidability like the sentence “*This statement is false*” even if we cannot solve it (as it is “outside” our consciousness). But as consciousness is “inside” us, *and* science, we cannot even start, it is prohibited by the very structure of science itself, just like the axioms of mathematics cannot be explained from “inside” math as they are its starting points. Perhaps a “superintelligence” (AI?) outside of us could “solve” the riddle of *our* consciousness, but then it could not explain it to *us*². It would be akin to explaining Schrödinger’s equation to a cat. That “superintelligence” could just as well be taken to simply be the (to us unknowable!) natural laws possibly underlying consciousness. But much more probably consciousness cannot be explained by natural laws *at all* - after all, “natural laws” are just inventions *our consciousness* uses to try to make some sense of the world, and consciousness is “outside” of science.

So, here goes:

The “scientific method” of Hypothesis → Tests → Better Hypothesis → New Tests → ... assumes at the outset that scientists are conscious, therefore consciousness can never be explained scientifically.

References

- [1] See, *e.g.*, F. Crick & J. Clark, *The astonishing hypothesis*, Journal of Consciousness Studies **1**, 10 (1994).
- [2] J. Hansson, *The magical “Born Rule” & quantum “measurement”: Implications for Physics*, Foundations **3**, 634 (2023). arXiv:2310.02283]
- [3] See, *e.g.*, T. Nagel, *Panpsychism*, in *Mortal questions*, pp. 181-195 (Cambridge University Press, 1979).
- [4] K. Gödel, *Über formal unentscheidbare Sätze der Principia Mathematica und verwandter Systeme I*, Monatshefte für Mathematik und Physik **38**, 173 (1931); *Zum intuitionistischen Aussagenkalkül*, Anzeiger Akademie der Wissenschaften Wien **38**, 65 (1932).

²The same goes if AI could find a TOE - a “Theory Of Everything”, the answer to Life, the Universe and Everything (42?) - we could never understand it.